

Kinetics of Thermal Decomposition of UO_3 , Part I. $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ *

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Kinetics of thermal decomposition of $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ has been studied thermogravimetrically. The decomposition has been found to proceed according to the scheme: $\alpha\text{-UO}_3 + \text{UO}_{2.9} \rightarrow \text{UO}_{2.67}$. The rate-dependent parameters, viz., the order of reaction n , activation energy ΔE , and entropy of activation ΔS for the two steps: (i) $\alpha\text{-UO}_3 \rightarrow \text{UO}_{2.9}$ and (ii) $\text{UO}_{2.9} \rightarrow \text{UO}_{2.67}$, have been determined.

Hoekstra and Siegel¹ reported five different modifications of UO_3 , in addition to an amorphous oxide. In view of the different crystal structures exhibited by the oxide with the same stoichiometry, it was decided to study the thermal stability of these oxides, particularly with reference to the kinetics of their decomposition to U_3O_8 ($\text{UO}_{2.67}$) and the role of crystal geometry on the observed kinetic behaviour. This communication deals with the kinetics of thermal decomposition of the hexagonal modification, $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$.

EXPERIMENTAL

The hexagonal form of UO_3 used in this investigation was obtained by the thermal decomposition of $\text{UO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, as reported by Cordfunke². The precipitate of uranyl peroxide, obtained from uranyl nitrate solution, was centrifuged, dried without washing, and heated at 400° for 3 hr. The $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ phase was confirmed from X-ray powder photograph taken with Philips camera (57 mm rad.) using filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. The sample was dried at 200° for 2 hr. before taking the photograph to get rid of the adsorbed moisture which varied with the time of its exposure to atmosphere. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out using the Sartorius thermobalance of 1 mg. sensitivity at a constant heating rate of $4^\circ/\text{min}$. The thermogravimetric results were supplemented by differential thermal analysis, employing the same heating rate. A Kipp and Zonen recorder (BD-1) was used for recording the differential curve³. O/U ratios were determined volumetrically⁴.

DISCUSSION

The thermogram (Fig. 1) shows that after the initial loss of adsorbed moisture, $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ decomposes by a two-step process, namely, $\alpha\text{-UO}_3 \rightarrow \text{UO}_{2.9} \rightarrow \text{UO}_{2.67}$. The decomposi-

*Presented at the 2nd Annual Convention of the Indian Chemical Society, held at Allahabad December 26-29, 1964.

1. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 18, 154.

2. *Ibid.*, 1961, 23, 285.

3. Deshpande and Karkhanavala, A.E.E.T./CD/3, 1962.

4. Newman, *ColL. Czech Chem. Comm.*, 1960, 25, 2235.

FIG. 1

tion of α - UO_3 starts at 420° , showing the intermediate step corresponding to $\text{UO}_{2.8}$ in the temperature range of 490° to 520° . $\text{UO}_{2.8}$ then decomposed to U_3O_8 ($\text{UO}_{2.67}$) resulting in a constant weight level beyond 640° . Differential thermal analysis curve for the sample also shows two endothermic peaks in addition to the one due to the loss of moisture. The small peak in the temperature range of 440° to 520° is attributed to the formation of $\text{UO}_{2.8}$. This is followed by a larger one, due to conversion of $\text{UO}_{2.8}$ to U_3O_8 ($\text{UO}_{2.67}$), in the range of 540° to 640° . Powder photographs taken of the samples quenched from 500° and of the composition $\text{UO}_{2.8}$ exhibit patterns very similar to that of α - UO_3 . Annealing of the substance with the composition $\text{UO}_{2.8}$ shows no change in the number of lines. A change in the relative intensities of lines is, however, observed, which

may be due to changes in crystallinity and preferred orientation.

A detailed kinetic study of the two steps of decomposition was carried out, using the methods of Horowitz and Metzger⁵ and of Coats and Redfern⁶. The order of reaction ' n ', the activation energy ΔE , and the frequency factor Z are shown⁵ by the relations:

$$F(m) = n^{1/(1-n)} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

for all values of n except 1; for $n=1$, $F(m) = 1/e$

$$\ln \ln (1 - \alpha)^{-1} = \frac{E_a}{R \cdot T_a^2} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$Z = \frac{\Delta E \cdot a}{R \cdot T_a^2} \exp. \frac{\Delta E}{R \cdot T_a} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$s = T - T_a \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where α is the fraction reacted at temperature T , ' a ' is the heating rate, and $F(m)$ is the fraction remaining unchanged at the temperature, T_a , at which the reaction rate is maximum.

5. *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, 35, 1464.

6. *Nature*, 1964, 201, 68.

$F(m)$ is obtained from the plot of W vs. T and T_s from the plot of rate of weight loss dW/dT vs. T . A typical plot for the reaction $UO_{2.9} \rightarrow U_3O_8$ is shown in Fig. 2. The order of reaction, determined by this method, is found to be unity for both the steps. The activation energy calculated from the plot of $\ln \ln (1-\alpha)^{-1}$ vs. θ (Fig. 3) is 92.8 kcal./mole for the first step and 109.1 kcal./mole for the second.

To confirm these values, use was also made of the equations developed by Coats and Redfern⁶. The general expression is

$$\log \left[\frac{1-(1-\alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n) T^n} \right] = -\frac{\Delta E}{2.3RT} + \log(Z.R.)/\alpha \Delta E \left[1 - (2RT/\Delta E) \right] \quad (5)$$

for all the values of n , except 1. For $n = 1$, the expression is

$$\log \left[-\log \frac{(1-\alpha)}{T^n} \right] = \frac{-\Delta E}{2.3RT} + \log(Z.R.)/\alpha \Delta E \left[1 - (2RT/\Delta E) \right] \quad (6)$$

The symbols have their usual significance. It can be shown that for most values of ΔE and the temperature spans, over which the reactions generally occur (i. e., about 50° to 100°), the expression:

$$\log \frac{Z.R.}{\alpha \Delta E} \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{\Delta E} \right]$$

FIG. 2. Tracing of the thermogravimetric curve (full line) in the range 520° to 650° and the differential curve (broken line) derived therefrom used in determination of $F(m)$ and T_s .

FIG. 3. The plots of $\ln \ln (1-\alpha)^{-1}$ vs. θ for the two decomp. steps, used for calculating ΔE .

is nearly constant. Hence if the reaction is of the zero or first order, the plot of

$$\log \alpha/T^n \text{ vs. } 1/T \text{ or of } \log \left[-\log \frac{(1-\alpha)}{T^n} \right] \text{ vs. } 1/T$$

should result in a straight line of slope $-\Delta E/2.3R$. As can be seen from Fig. 4, the first step of the reaction fits the equation for zero-order kinetics, whereas the second step shows

good agreement with the equation for first order. The activation energies thus calculated are 31.6 and 106.9 kcal./mole for the first and the second step, respectively.

FIG. 4. The plots for zero and first order kinetics following the method of Coates and Redfern.

$$\text{For } n=1: y = -\log \left[-\log \frac{(1-\alpha)}{T^2} \right]$$

$$\text{For } n=0: y = -\log \frac{\alpha}{T^2}$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta E - T\Delta S \quad \dots (7)$$

The entropy of activation is related to the frequency factor, Z , by the relation⁸:

$$Z = (kT/h) \cdot \exp \Delta S/R \quad \dots (8)$$

where k and h are Boltzman's and Plank's constant, respectively, other symbols having their usual meaning⁸. The frequency factors calculated from equation (3) of Horowitz and Metzger⁵ for first and the second step are 1.05×10^7 and 1.4×10^{14} sec.⁻¹, respectively. From these values the entropy of activation, ΔS , for the two steps were found to be -27.53 and 50.03 e.u., respectively. Thus the high rate of decomposition observed in the second step can now be explained on the basis of free energy of activation which is minimised due to a large positive contribution from the entropy of activation term.

An additional abnormal feature of the second stage of reaction is the high value of the frequency factor. Though such high values are not rare in solid state reactions⁹, it was decided to check this value by carrying out a separate experiment. $\text{UO}_{2.5}$ (1g.) was taken in a platinum boat and was introduced into a furnace maintained at 600°. The decom-

⁸ Over the temperature range of decomposition of $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ (420° to 640°) the factor kT/h in equation (8) is assumed to be 10^{13} .

7. Jacobs and Tompkins, "Chemistry of Solid State", (Ed. W. E. Garner), Butterworth Scientific Publications, p. 188, 1955.

8. Glasstone, "Text Book of Physical Chemistry", Macmillan and Co. Ltd., pp 1103, 1955.

9. Garner, Ref. 7, p. 220.

position was found to go to completion in a minute. As the sample could not be heated to less than a minute accurately, the time for completion of the reaction was taken as 1 min. The specific reaction rate, K_1 , worked out on this basis, is $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. On substituting this value in the relation:

$$K_1 = Z \cdot \exp \frac{-\Delta E}{RT} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

the value of Z works out as $1.55 \times 10^{15} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, in reasonable agreement with the value of $1.4 \times 10^{14} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, obtained by using Horowitz and Metzger's equation⁵.

It is concluded from the present observations that $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ decomposes according to the scheme: $\alpha\text{UO}_3 \rightarrow \text{UO}_{2.9} \rightarrow \text{UO}_{2.67}$. The first step shows more agreement with zero-order kinetics, whereas the decomposition of $\text{UO}_{2.9}$ to $\text{UO}_{2.67}$ is governed by the first-order rate law. The average values of activation energies are 32.2 and 108 kcal./mole for the first and the second step, respectively. The entropy of activation for the first step is negative with a value of -27.53 e.u., whereas for the second stage it is 50.03 e.u. As the X-ray powder patterns of $\alpha\text{-UO}_3$ and $\text{UO}_{2.9}$ are identical and further since the infrared patterns of the two show close similarity¹, there is reason to believe that the first step is a simple topochemical reaction¹⁰.

The second step of the reaction is more complex and involves a high pre-exponential factor. Normally the decomposition of solids proceeds by the formation and growth of product nuclei. Simple decompositions of this type usually follow first-order kinetics though fractional orders are not rare¹¹. The decomposition of $\text{UO}_{2.9}$ to $\text{UO}_{2.67}$ also follows first-order kinetics. The abnormally high values of the pre-exponential factor cannot, however, be explained on the basis of simple nucleation and growth process. In order to account for the abnormal values in such decompositions Hill¹² has recently proposed a theory, according to which such transformations are governed by diffusion and nucleation processes, so that the boundary between the reactant and product phases is really a diffuse layer containing many growing product nuclei with a range of sizes. The applicability of Hill's theory to reactions of the type, reported in this communication, is being investigated, as normally diffusion-controlled processes do not follow the first-order kinetics.

Authors wish to thank Dr. J. Shankar for his helpful suggestions.

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Received November 4, 1965.

10. Shannon and Rossi, *Nature*, 1964, 202, 1000.

11. Garner, Ref. 7, p. 224.

12. Hill, "Reactivity of Solids", (Ed. J. De Boer, 1961), pp 294-300, Elsevier Publishing Co.